

A Study on Employee Quality of Work Life Done at Supreme Coated Board Mills Private Limited (SCBMPL), Sivakasi

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Abstract

The world is moving with fast and dealing with an organization has turned become more critical than any other time in recent times. There is a challenge between organizations to pull in quality human asset so as to be ahead its rivals in a specific industry. At this background, Quality of Work Life (QWL) has developed as one of the imperative part of employment. The primary aim of the project report “A Study on Employee Quality of Work Life done at Supreme Coated Board Mills Private Ltd” is to investigate the Quality of Work Life and to explore the main factors that affect employees in the company. The survey questions designed to determine four elements of QWL i.e. factor influencing, work environment, inter relationship and employee satisfaction. The survey was dispersed to respondents and the reactions were accumulated. The responses given by the respondents were dissected and presented using different statistical tools such as Percentage analysis, weighted arithmetic mean, chi square analysis and Garrett ranking technique. Quality of Work Life in Supreme Coated Board Mills Private Limited (SCBMPL) is considered to be the most critical aspect. The management has to look up the facilities that employees are provided with personal, physical and spiritual working environment, will lead for higher productivity in the organization.

Introduction

Nature of quality work life work is a process in organizations, which enables its members at all levels to participate actively and efficiently in shaping the organizations environment, methods and outcomes. It is a value based process, which is pointed towards meeting the twin goals of upgraded effectiveness of organization and improved Quality of work life at work for employees. This study is attempted to understand the impact of QWL on employee satisfaction and organizational productivity with special reference to SCBMPL.

Coverage of the study

This study covers the Quality of Work Life among the employees in Supreme Coated Board Mills Private Limited, Sivakasi. It covers the factors influence Quality of Work Life are working Condition, job security, grievance handling and job satisfaction.

Objectives

- To examine the factor influencing the Quality of Work Life
- To know the working environment of the organization
- To analyse the inter relationship between workers, supervisors and management
- To know the overall employee satisfaction towards SCBMPL

Hypotheses

Hypothesis is a tentative proposition formulated for empirical testing. The study is explorative in nature. In order to understand the salary paid based on the responsibilities the following hypothesis has been formulated. They are:

- There is a relationship between gender of the respondents and salary paid based on their responsibilities.

Methodology

The study is based on the analysis of both primary and secondary data. The primary data needed for this study is collected from the employees. The secondary data needed for study is collected from various magazines, articles published in newspapers and surfing through network.

Tools for Analysis

- Percentage
- Weighted Arithmetic Mean
- Chi-Square Test
- Garrett Ranking Technique

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between Gender and Salary of the respondent.

Analysis of Data

There is a relationship between Gender of the Respondents and Salary paid based on their responsibilities. Chi-Square test is used to as a tool to test it. Chi square test table are as follows

O _i	E _i	O _i -E _i	(O _i -E _i) ²	X ²
7	5.5	1.5	2.25	0.41
10	12.6	2.6	6.76	0.54
7	7.14	0.14	0.02	2.00
10	10.5	0.5	0.25	0.02
8	6.3	1.7	2.89	0.46
6	7.54	1.54	2.37	0.31
20	17.4	2.6	6.76	0.39
10	9.86	0.14	0.02	0.00
15	14.5	0.5	0.25	0.02
7	8.7	1.7	2.89	0.33
Total				2.49

Degree of freedom = (r-1) (c-1) = (3-1) (3-1) = 4

Table value (X_{2 e}) = 9.488

Since X_{2o} < X_{2e} it is evident from the above table that, there is no significant relationship

between the Gender of the Respondents and Salary paid based on their responsibilities. So the null hypothesis accepted.

Factors Affecting Work Environment

The researcher has used the Garrett's Ranking method for ranking the factors affecting work environment about quality of work life.

S.No.	Particulars	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	Total
1	Heat	17	10	5	11	6	8	43	100
2	Cold	18	17	6	6	16	30	7	100
3	Noise	5	3	22	10	28	17	15	100
4	Inadequate ventilation	8	23	10	37	7	6	9	100
5	Dirtness of work environment	15	20	19	6	15	15	10	100
6	Heavy lifting	17	24	10	20	6	17	6	100
7	Lack of space	20	7	18	14	16	9	16	100
Total		100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Respondents are asked to rank the unconsciousness of shoppers on factors affecting work environment. Based on the ranks that the respondents awarded, the researcher has found the number of responses placed in each rank.

Ranking for Factors Affecting Working Environment on Quality of Work Life

Garrett's Score

S.No	Particulars	Garrett Score	Average Score	Garrett Rank
1	Heat	4302	43.02	VII
2	Cold	5036	50.36	V
3	Noise	4476	44.76	VI
4	Inadequate ventilation	5431	54.31	II
5	Dirtness of work environment	5267	52.67	III
6	Heavy lifting	5458	54.58	I
7	Lack of space	5112	51.12	IV

Source: Computed Data

This table I shows the Garrett scores and average scores. The averages are ranked according to their values. The primary position is given to "Heavy lifting"(54.58) and the last rank is given to "Heat"(43.02). Therefore the employees feel that their working environment is heat.

Findings

- Half of the respondents having below 5 years of experience in their current position.
- A Majority of 48 per cent of the respondents opines that, the relationship with their superior is good.
- A Majority of 38 per cent of the respondents are agree that, the communication with their co-workers is good.
- A Majority of 53 per cent of the respondents opines that, the organization provide all the benefits.

- A Majority of 43 per cent of the respondents are agree that, the training program is helpful for their future career.
- A Majority of 43 per cent of the respondents are agree that, the company is paying adequate and fair compensation for their workers.
- A Majority of 58 per cent of the respondents are says that, the grievance redressed system is giving proper solution for their problem.
- A Majority of 43 per cent of the respondents are satisfied with the solution given by the grievance redressed system.
- A Majority of 30 per cent of the respondents are not satisfied due to delay in time.

Suggestion

- For Employee satisfaction, the grievance redressal committee should opt the solution to the problems within the stipulated time without any delay.
- Additional number of employees should be appointed to reduce the work overload as well as to increase the performance of the workers.
- The organization can take proper steps to avoid heat generation, latrines and urinals facilities in their work environment.

Conclusion

Work life balance refers to the inter relationship between employees and work place. It is the degree of excellent brought through work and working condition which contributes to the overall satisfaction at the individual and the organizational level. Administration practices that, evident concern about employee's job security, conducive working conditions, fair and equitable wages and participation of the worker representatives from the formal association in decision making process will lead to a harmonious industrial relation in the working place. To enhance quality work life and improvised productivity, many Indian companies have tested and skill experimented on their quality of work life policies. The development activities of quality of work life lead to better work environment and increased productivity.